

Exploring ChatGPT’s Capacity for Modal Subordination Via Discourse Representation Theory

Chunxi Luo, Diya Goel
University of Edinburgh

Abstract. The inherent ambiguity of language presents a challenge to natural language understanding, with modal subordination being one such scenario. The scope of modals, especially those that codify certainty and possibility, gives language the ability to express hypothetical worlds through basic modal logic. This paper will compare the human understanding of modal subordination using Discourse Representation Theory, with the capacity of ChatGPT 3.5 to understand such ambiguity. This is done by asking ChatGPT 3.5 to complete tasks that test its ability to resolve modal subordination, including but not limiting to asking the existence of a discourse referent, and choosing true propositions given a modal scenario. Our results will demonstrate that ChatGPT 3.5 tends to follow the behaviour of modal subordination in clear-cut cases per Discourse Representation Theory, but falls short when pragmatic elements are introduced, or when there exist two modalities.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; modal subordination; Discourse Representation Theory

1 Introduction

The inherent ambiguity of language presents a challenge to natural language understanding, with modal subordination being one such scenario. The scope of modals, especially those that codify certainty and possibility, gives language the ability to express hypothetical worlds through basic modal logic. This is crucial in languages, as this allows us to reason with hypotheticals, which coincides with one of Hockett’s design features of communication (Hockett & Hockett, 1960).

With the rise of Large Language Models (LLMs), one question arises: can LLMs process language with the same rate of efficiency and accuracy as humans? A part of the answer relies on the capacity of LLMs to process and reasonably function within hypothetical spaces. We have chosen modal subordination as the avenue for exploring this within ChatGPT 3.5, a popular LLM. This paper will thus argue that ChatGPT in particular does not exhibit the same capacity as humans when processing modal subordination utterances, by comparing the human understanding of modal subordination using Discourse Representation Theory, with the capacity of ChatGPT 3.5 to understand such ambiguity, through probing techniques that are inspired by previous papers exploring the capacities of LLMs (Chatterjee & Schockaert, 2023).

2 Theoretical Background

Dynamic semantics is a particular branch of semantic theory that expands on static semantics, by allowing scenarios to be updated with new information as the discourse progresses. One of the earliest forms of

dynamic semantics is Discourse Representation Theory (DRT: Kamp, 1981). This section will give a brief overview of DRT and how it can be applied to resolving the ambiguity of modal subordination.

2.1 Discourse Representation Theory

Discourse Representation Theory (DRT) is a method for keeping track of utterances in discourse. Each new utterance either introduces new characters known as “discourse referents”, or updates the descriptions of the stage and the relations between the discourse referents.

DRT expands on the truth-conditional meaning approach to account for pragmatic influences, and allows for formal semantics to deal with phenomena such as scope ambiguity, donkey anaphora and, as discussed below, modal subordination.

Below, we will give an example of DRT at work. Consider this set of utterances:

- (1) John has a cat.
- (2) It is black.

The first sentence introduces two discourse referents – John and a cat, and expresses a relation of ownership from John to the cat. This is expressed symbolically as below; the discourse referents are marked at the top, whilst the predicates that describe the scenario are detailed underneath the referents.

<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>
John(<i>x</i>)	
cat(<i>y</i>)	
have(<i>x</i> , <i>y</i>)	

In more detail, this sentence introduces two discourse referents into the scenario – *x* and *y*. *x* is given the property “John(*x*)”, *y* is given the property “cat(*y*)”, and the relation between the two referents is expressed using “have(*x*, *y*)”.

The second sentence starts with an “it”. This anaphora can be resolved by looking at the referents and their properties. Since “it” signifies that the referent must be an animal, and only “*y*” among the current referents satisfies this condition, the sentence thus updates the property of *y*. This is expressed as below.

<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>
John(<i>x</i>)	
cat(<i>y</i>)	
have(<i>x</i> , <i>y</i>)	
black(<i>y</i>)	

These boxes are called “Discourse Representation Structure” (DRS: Kamp, 1981). One can think of them as scopes. This is exemplified by the following example.

- (3) Every student takes a test.

This sentence corresponds to two readings, and thus we can craft two different DRSs. The first reading is narrow scope, in which the universal quantifier scopes over “student”, indicating that there is one test that every student takes. This is represented as follows:

The narrow scope meant that there is only one discourse referent introduced in the main DRS — the test, since that is the only concrete individual in the sentence. Thus, referent t is introduced and given the property “test(t)”.

To proceed, the narrow scope reading can be rephrased as “If there is a student, they will take the test.” This can be done by introducing two new DRSs, one corresponding to the antecedent and one to the consequent.

The antecedent scenario “there is a student” can be constructed per the process of the first example. Since this scenario is a hypothetical that exists within realm of the whole sentence, we put that DRS inside the main DRS. The consequent scenario “they take the test” does not introduce any new referents; thus, the top part of the DRS remains blank, and the relation between the referent introduced in the antecedent and the main DRS is expressed with “take(x,t)”. These scenarios are linked by using the implication symbol.

The wide scope — where the universal quantifier scopes over the entire sentence — is different from the narrow scope, as there are no referents introduced in the main sentence. This is because there are no concrete individuals. The full DRS is expressed as follows:

The scope ambiguity thus is expressed through the existence of discourse referents in either the main DRS or the consequent DRS.

The example above shows that DRSs can be combined with logic symbols to express complex meaning. This will prove crucial to express modal subordination in the next section.

2.2 Modal Subordination

Modal subordination refers to the phenomenon where modality carries over across sentences (Roberts, 1989). For example, consider the following sentences:

- (4) Jack might eat an ice-cream.

(5) It will be chocolate.

Here, the first sentence indicates that the utterance “eat an ice-cream” and the corresponding discourse referents is inside a “possible world”; in other words, it is enclosed in the possibility modality. This possibility carries to the next sentence; though normally the modal “will” signifies certainty or future, here it extends in the meaning into “if Jack actually did eat an ice-cream, that ice-cream will have to be chocolate”. By itself, sentence (5) does not carry the modality of possibility; however, the combination of (4) and (5) changes this.

We can explain this phenomenon by using modal logic symbols in DRT. Below, the \Box will represent “certainty”, while the \Diamond will represent “possibility”. Sentence (4) introduces the referent “Jack” in the common ground. However, since the predicate “eat an ice-cream” is under the scope of the possibility modality, the “ice-cream” referent is being introduced not in the common ground, but in the “world”, or DRS, inside the possibility modality. This is represented as follows:

Sentence (5) thus exhibits modal subordination by simply updating the DRS inside the scope of the possibility modality, as follows:

3 Methodology

In order to investigate if ChatGPT 3.5 can correctly identify and process modal subordination, we crafted several scenarios, detailed below, that test its capacity of doing so.

3.1 Existence Scenario

This is the simplest of the four scenarios that will be tested on ChatGPT 3.5 is the “existence scenario”. This tests whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 knows where to instantiate new discourse referents. This is showcased in the following example:

- (6) There is a garden where only two types of flowers bloom, roses and tulips. It’s said that
“There may be a rose in the garden. It will blossom under the full moon.”
It is now the full moon. What will happen in the garden?

The correct analysis of this scenario is as follows: The sentence fragment “In a garden where only two types of flowers bloom, roses and tulips”, the common ground DRS is introduced with a new referent: m , referring to the garden. The next sentence, “there may be a rose in the garden”, updates a new DRS inside the common ground DRS, and the new discourse referent “ x ” — the “rose” — is instantiated inside the modality DRS instead of the common ground DRS. This is because one cannot discern that there is indeed a rose in the garden; instead, only the possibility is being discussed. The following sentence “It will blossom under the full moon” thus creates a conditional shown in the common ground DRS, and the final sentence “It is now the full moon” updates the common ground DRS with the $\text{fullmoon}(m)$ property, meaning “there is a full moon in m ”.

There will be 20 questions that follow this pattern.

Figure 1: *Existence scenario DRS.*

Thus, if ChatGPT 3.5 instantiates new discourse referents correctly, the answer should be “There is not enough information,” as no roses are instantiated in the common ground DRS. Otherwise, there is a high probability that ChatGPT 3.5 incorrectly updated the new referent in the common ground DRS.

3.2 Scope Scenario

The “scope scenario” aims to test whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 recognizes that the additional information does not update the common ground DRS, but instead the DRS inside the scope of the modality operator. The following example shows an instance of the prompt used to test this behaviour:

- (7) Imagine a universe in which there are two bookstores only: Blackwells and Waterstones.
Now, consider this utterance: “John has bought a book. If the book is from Blackwells,
then the book must be a mystery novel. The book would be red.”

Given this utterance, if the book is from Waterstones, is it red?

The correct analysis of this scenario is as follows: The first paragraph sets up the common ground DRS, and instantiates the discourse referents *b* (Blackwells), *w* (Waterstones), and their respective identities. The next utterance “John has bought a book” introduces two more referents *j* (John), *x* (book) and their relationships. Continuing to look at the scenario, the next utterance updates the DRS with a conditional.

The next utterance “The book would be red” is crucial. A person that correctly interprets this scenario needs to realize that this is talking about the hypothetical scenario in which the book is from Blackwells, and thus the property of “the book is red” should be updated in the consequent DRS of the conditional, instead of the common ground DRS. This is why, after updating the common ground DRS with the information that “the book is from Waterstones” from the question, the correct answer is “There is not enough information.”, as there is no indication shown in the DRS about the book’s colour when it is from Waterstones.

Figure 2: Scope scenario DRS.

If a person updated the information of “the book is red” in the wrong scope, i.e. at the common ground DRS, then they would answer incorrectly, saying “Yes, the book is red”. Thus, this shows that these types of questions are adequate in testing whether or not ChatGPT can update information in the right scope, when faced with a modal subordination construction.

There will be 20 questions that follow this pattern.

3.3 Double Modality

The “double modality scenario” aims to test whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 can process two modalities in a stream of utterances that exhibit modal subordination correctly. The following example shows an instance of the prompt used to test this behaviour:

- (8) Consider this utterance: “Kevin will bake a cake. It could be chocolate.” Which of the following is possible?
 - (a) After some time, Kevin baked a chocolate cake.

- (b) There isn't a time where Kevin baked a cake.
- (c) After some time, Kevin baked a vanilla cake.

The correct analysis is as follows: The first utterance states a necessity modal DRS, and thus the common ground DRS is updated as such. The second utterance updated the common ground DRS with the conditional expressed through modal subordination. In this scenario, the necessity operator means that it is necessary that Kevin will bake a cake some point in time, thus (b) is incorrect. As for (a) and (c), both should be possible, as the consequent of the conditional in the common ground DRS is only a possibility modal.

A wrong analysis can occur if the analyser did not correctly recognize that there is another modality outside of the modal subordination, or that this modality does not interact with the conditional created through modal subordination. There will be 22 questions that follow this pattern.

Figure 3: Double modality DRS.

3.4 Pragmatics Scenario

The “pragmatics scenario” aims to test whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 can process deontic modality in the framework of an ideal world, instead of the real world. The following example shows an instance of the prompt used to test this behaviour:

- (9) Consider this utterance: “Employees must attend the mandatory training session. It could enhance their skills.” In an ideal world where everyone follows the rules, which of the following is possible?
 - (a) Alfred attended the training session and enhanced his skills.
 - (b) Alfred did not attend the training session and enhanced his skills.
 - (c) Alfred attended the training session and did not enhance his skills.
 - (d) Alfred did not attend the training session and did not enhance his skills.

The analysis is the same as the previous section. The crucial idea that an analyser needs to realize is that though the modality expressed here is deontic, the prompt is asking the analyser to analyse this case in the ideal world where everyone follows the rules. Thus, choice (a) and (c) are the only possible ones.

An analyser that cannot reason in a given framework, in this case the ideal world, will wrongly suggest that all four options are possible.

There will be 20 questions that follow this pattern.

Figure 4: Pragmatics scenario DRS.

4 Results

4.1 Existence Scenario

Table 1: Results of existence scenario questions.

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	18	0
Wrong Logic	2	0

The table above shows the result of the existence scenario questions. All questions are answered correctly by ChatGPT 3.5, and taking in account of the probabilistic nature of ChatGPT 3.5, there is a high probability that ChatGPT 3.5 did indeed process where it should instantiate new discourse referents in the DRS correctly.

4.2 Scope Scenario

Table 2: Results of scope scenario questions.

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	15	0
Wrong Logic	5	0

The table above shows the result of the scope scenario questions. All questions are answered correctly by ChatGPT 3.5, and taking in account the probabilistic nature of ChatGPT 3.5, there is a high probability that ChatGPT 3.5 did indeed “understand” where to update new information in the DRS correctly. However, we do see a decrease in logic correctness when comparing this to the existence scenario above, though again this can be considered variation due to the probabilistic nature of ChatGPT.

4.3 Double Modality Scenario

The table above shows the result of the double modality scenario questions. Here, one can see that ChatGPT is now having problems in processing two modals in the context of modal subordination.

Table 3: *Results of double modality scenario questions.*

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	4	12
Wrong Logic	1	5

Only five out of 22 questions are answered correctly.

After an analysis of the wrong answers, we have discovered that the most common mistake that ChatGPT has done is modal substitution — that is, substituting a necessity modal operator with a possibility one, or vice versa. This suggests that ChatGPT may have wrongly concluded that in the DRS framework, two modalities will affect each other.

4.4 Pragmatics Scenario

Table 4: *Results of pragmatic scenario questions.*

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	0	0
Wrong Logic	1	19

The table above shows the result of the pragmatics scenario questions. As evidenced from results above, one can see that ChatGPT almost always ignored the limitation to reason in the ideal world “where everyone follows the rules”, and instead preferred to reason in the framework of the real world.

5 Discussion

From our experiments, it can be seen that though ChatGPT can correctly analyse basic modality scenarios with one modal operation, it fails at handling more complex modality scenarios, as well as having trouble in interpreting modality situations in the established universe the user has given it.

What this implies is that ChatGPT may have trouble in processing more complex hypothetical scenarios, as seen from the third set of questions, or a blatant refusal of considering hypothetical universes, as seen from the fourth set of questions. While the latter might be preferable in some contexts, this still shows the possibility that ChatGPT cannot properly reason hypothetical utterances in the framework of other hypothetical universes that are different from the real world.

If ChatGPT can be said to understand languages, it must be able to process and analyse complex hypothetical scenarios. Our research suggests that this goal has not been reached yet.

This paper is an attempt to contribute to reasonable and explainable Natural Language Processing (NLP), or explainable AI (XAI), from a linguistics perspective. Many attempts at XAI require a foundation

in computer science, and often times ways to dissect how AI interprets language from a perspective other than computer science is ignored. Through our research, we have demonstrated a possible way for linguistics, specifically semantics, to contribute more to the development of XAI and explainable NLP processes.

Limitations of our research exist. ChatGPT is constantly learning and evolving, and due to financial limitations, we cannot feasibly do this experiment in ChatGPT 4 or later versions. It would be an interesting avenue to take to compare diachronically if ChatGPT improved in reasoning in hypothetical scenarios. Another avenue that could be explored is synchronous comparisons. Due to time limitations, we are not able to compare results from different large language models (LLMs). To reiterate, it would be an interesting direction to take for future research, to compare different LLMs in terms of their capacity in reasoning hypothetical scenarios.

6 Conclusion

We have shown that there is non-trivial evidence that suggests ChatGPT cannot properly process hypothetical scenarios through probing using scenarios that used modal subordination structures. Evidence has supported our thesis, in that though ChatGPT can process simple scenarios involving one modal, scenarios more complex than that will run into logical errors or inconsistencies.

7 References

- Chatterjee, U., & Schockaert, S. (2023, August). *Probing the conceptual space of chatgpt and gpt-4*.
- Hockett, C. F., & Hockett, C. D. (1960). The origin of speech. *Scientific American*, 203 (3), 88–97. Retrieved June 29, 2024, from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24940617>
- Kamp, H. (1981). A theory of truth and semantic representation. In J. Groenendijk, T. Janssen, & M. Stokhof (Eds.), *Formal methods in the study of language* (pp. 277-322). Amsterdam: Mathematical Centre.
- Roberts, C. (1989). Modal subordination and pronominal anaphora in discourse. *Linguistics and Philosophy*, 12 (6), 683–721. Retrieved February 14, 2024, from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25001367>